

Evaluating the Effects of Activity-Based Learning on Attainment of Course Outcomes for Third-Year B.Tech Students: A Case Study

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Abstract— This article presents a comprehensive case study conducted on third-year B.Tech Biotechnology students who faced significant disruptions in their education due to the COVID-induced lockdown. As a result, they missed out on first three semesters of in-person learning and had to adapt to a sudden transition from online to offline mode of education. Many struggled to cope with the shift from virtual classes to physical classrooms. Lack of familiarity, distractions, and diminished interest were observed, leading to lower grades and reduced academic performance. Therefore, this study focuses on evaluating the impact of activity-based learning on the students' ability to adjust to offline classes and improve their course outcomes. The study examines two courses, to assess the effects of activity-based learning on students' classroom engagement, learning, and participation. The following activities were implemented in the study: game-based learning, LCM model-based discussions, flipped classroom, and various in-class activities. The findings revealed a direct correlation between the number of activities incorporated, and the students' course outcomes. However, the study also identified certain challenges. Students exhibited a lack of self-motivation and required additional incentives to encourage their active participation in the activities. Addressing this issue is crucial to sustain the positive effects of activity-based learning. In conclusion, this case study provides empirical evidence supporting the effectiveness of activity-based learning in enhancing the attainment of course outcomes for third-year B.Tech Biotechnology students. By incorporating engaging activities into the learning process, educators can help students overcome challenges associated with disrupted education and improve their academic performance.

Keywords—Activity based learning, Course outcomes, Student engagement, Engineering education, Game based learning, Flipped classroom, LCM Model

I. INTRODUCTION

The present study focuses on the experiences with the current final year B.Tech students during their prefinal year of study, spanning from July 2022 to April 2023. These students embarked on their college education amidst the challenging circumstances imposed by the COVID-induced lockdown. Initially, their first year commenced online, necessitating the use of gadgets such as mobile phones and laptops. Unfortunately, due to bandwidth issues, students faced limitations in interacting with their peers, rarely being able to see each other during online classes. Moreover, the examination process conducted online presented a potential breeding ground for malpractices and plagiarism. As the college reopened for the fourth semester, students encountered numerous challenges in transitioning to physical classrooms, leading to low attendance rates during the initial semesters.

Moreover, distractions posed by the persistent use of gadgets remained a prevalent issue, hindering their engagement in class. Subsequently, a recurring pattern emerged where students failed to submit assignments, often attributing their inability to participate in learning activities to the repercussions of the COVID-induced lockdown. Consequently, instructors were compelled to devise innovative techniques to enhance student engagement within the classroom. The adoption of hybrid learning approaches aimed to address the students' low participation levels in activities and assignments. This study explores the impact of these strategies on improving student engagement and participation, as well as their academic performance.

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly disrupted the field of education, necessitating a swift transition to online learning to mitigate the impact of lockdown measures [1]–[3]. However, recent reports [4],[5] have shed light on the challenges faced by students in higher education, including increased anxiety, loneliness, and other mental stresses arising from the COVID-induced lockdown, especially among UG students [6]. While studies conducted in other countries, such as Peru, have shown significant improvements in academic performance during online learning, this was often attributed to the suspension of other activities, allowing students to focus solely on their studies [7]. In contrast, in India, where most students are primarily focused on academics and do not have part-time jobs, this aspect may not yield similar results.

Online learning platforms have demonstrated benefits for introverted learners, with some individuals opting to remain as "digital residents" in these environments [8]. However, it is worth noting that not all students favor online learning, leading to suggestions of integrating offline elements to create a more holistic educational experience [9], [10].

Various studies have highlighted the positive impact of gamification on engineering students' motivation, academic performance [11], [12] and problem solving skills [13]. Additionally, the use of online and offline case discussions has proven effective in enhancing learning outcomes in computer science postgraduate courses [14]. Interactive activities implemented through Jupyter Notebook have shown promising results in improving academic performance and engagement among Chemical Engineering students [15]. Similarly, collaborative learning approaches have yielded improved test results for Mechanical Engineering students [16], [17].

In light of these observations and the unique context of the current study, it becomes imperative to explore the impact of activity-based learning on the adjustment, engagement, and

academic outcomes of third-year B.Tech Biotechnology students. By addressing the challenges of disrupted education and leveraging the potential benefits of interactive learning approaches, this study aims to provide insights into effective strategies for enhancing students' educational experiences, academic achievements, and ultimately, the attainment of course outcomes (CO).

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Student Groups

The participants in this study were the pre-final year B.Tech Biotechnology students, who are currently in their final year. The total student population in this group consisted of 47 individuals. This particular student group was chosen due to their unique circumstances and challenges faced in readjusting to normalcy after the reopening of the college.

B. Courses

The author served as the instructor for two 2-credit courses: 19B504 Enzyme Engineering and Technology and 19B604 Bioprocess Design and Economics. Table I provides an overview of the course outcomes, as well as the teaching and evaluation levels associated with each course.

C. Activities

The activities provided to the students, along with the evaluation rubrics and their participation percentages, are summarized in Table II. The activities encompassed two types: classroom activities and online activities. Online activities were designed for individual completion, while classroom activities were conducted in groups of either 2 or 5 students, formed randomly. Various online tools, as listed in Table II, were utilized to facilitate these activities. For online discussions, the LxI (Learning Experience Interaction) framework from the LCM (Learner Centric MOOC) model was adapted, incorporating a focus question and a reflection quiz as described elsewhere [18].

To enhance student participation, bonus points were awarded for the Multiple Choice Question (MCQ) component of the Continuous Assessment, details of which are also presented in Table II. In instances where no activities were performed, traditional teaching methods such as lectures, assignments, and class quizzes were employed to deliver course content to the students. Further details regarding these traditional methods are not provided in this context.

D. Impact on Student Performance and Attainment of Course Outcomes

To evaluate the impact of activities on student performance, the pass percentage and the percentage attainment (based on average marks) for each course outcome were assessed across three continuous assessment tests.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following sections discuss the results of this study.

A. Student Performance and Course Outcomes

The relationship between the attainment of course outcomes, pass percentage, and the number of activities is illustrated in Fig. 1, encompassing both courses. The data reveals a positive correlation between the number of activities and pass percentage, as well as the attainment of course outcomes. Higher levels of student participation in activities

generally corresponded to increased pass percentages and course outcome attainment, consistent with the literature [12].

TABLE I. COURSES AND COURSE OUTCOMES

CO No.	Description of CO	Teaching and Evaluation level
Enzyme Engineering and Technology		
1	Select and exploit suitable enzyme sources, their isolation, purification and characterization techniques for various commercial application purpose.	Knowledge Comprehension
2	Comprehend and apply enzyme kinetic models and inhibition kinetics for process development.	Comprehension Apply
3	Distinguish different immobilization techniques, their merits and demerits in industrial production with emphasis on surface immobilization kinetics.	Knowledge Comprehension
4	Identify and explain the various types of enzyme based biosensors for different applications	Knowledge Comprehension
5	Analyze various enzyme engineering methods for functional and stability improvement and use of enzyme based reactions in organic solvents.	Analyze
Bioprocess Design and Economics		
1	Describe the various requirements and regulations of a bioprocess industry	Apply
2	Define the types of design and design components of process industries	Apply, Analyse, Design, Evaluate
3	Describe and carry out optimization studies for process designs	Apply, Analyse, Design, Evaluate
4	Describe Biosafety regulations for operation of process industries	Apply, Analyse, Design, Evaluate
5	Perform cost and profitability calculations of process designs	Analyse, Evaluate

However, it is noteworthy that in certain instances, despite a high number of activities, there were dips observed in the pass percentage and course outcome attainment. Upon further examination, it was evident that these dips coincided with a low level of student participation. This suggests that active engagement and involvement of students in the activities are crucial factors influencing their performance and course outcome attainment. Interestingly, an analysis of the data also revealed that certain course outcomes exhibited high pass percentages and course outcome attainment, despite no activities performed, owing to their lower level of teaching or evaluation.

B. Student Participation and Preferences

Student participation plays a crucial role in the success of activity-based learning approaches. This section discusses the findings related to student participation and preferences, as illustrated in fig. 2.

The bubble diagram in fig. 2 provides a visual representation of the level of student participation in activities. Notably, students displayed a clear preference for classroom activities over online activities. It was observed that students were less inclined to engage in activities that involved more serious tasks, such as flowsheeting, which required learning a specific software. This hesitation may be attributed to concerns about the perceived complexity or unfamiliarity of such activities, in line with findings in the literature [11].

One interesting finding was related to the quiz games. Initially, students expressed apprehension and displayed a lower level of participation in the first quiz game, despite the offer of bonus points. However, in the subsequent quiz game,

TABLE II. DETAILS OF STUDENT ACTIVITIES

Course Name	CO	Activity	Mode of activity (Classroom/Online) (Group/Individual)	Description of activity	Tools used	Rubrics for evaluation	Additional incentives	Percentage of participation
Enzyme Engineering and Technology	1	Discussion 1	Online Individual	Discussion based on viscous fermentation broth	Padlet	5 points + 5 points for reflection quiz		Discussion – 51.06 RQ – 68.09
		Concept Mapping	Classroom Group	Submit a concept map based on the different types of bioproducts	Coggle	Map - 5 points + Speed - 5 points		70.22
Bioprocess Design and Economics	1	Discussion 2	Online Individual	Discussion based on viscous fermentation broth	Padlet	5 points	Best answer - 1 bonus point	38.30
		Discussion 3	Online Individual	Discussion based on economic impact analysis	Padlet	5 points	Best answer - 1 bonus point	48.94
		Quiz Game 1	Online Individual	Play a quiz game on process industry regulations	Blooket	10 points	Best player – 1 point	34.04
		Design problem	Classroom Group	Identify and submit a design for downstream processing	Pen & paper	10 points		55.32
	2	Flowsheeting	Online Individual	Perform software simulation and submit flowsheets	DWSIM	10 points		29.79
		Flipped classroom	Classroom Group	Set a question paper on “Bioprocess regulations”	Pen & paper	Quality of question paper – 5 points + Answers – 5 points		76.60
	3	Quiz Game 2	Online Individual	Play a quiz game on process optimisation	Blooket	10 points	Best player – 1 point	59.57
		Discussion 4	Online Individual	Discussion based on regulations in bioprocess industries	Padlet	5 points	Best answer - 1 bonus point	40.43

the level of participation increased. It is plausible that students were motivated by the enjoyable nature of the game, consistent with findings in the literature [17].

Fig. 1. Correlation between the number of activities and their level of participation on pass percentage, CO attainment

This highlights the importance of incorporating elements of enjoyment and entertainment into activities to encourage student engagement. Therefore it is important to consider students' preferences when integrating gamified elements into assessments, as evidenced by the study conducted by Udeozor et al. [17], which indicated engineering students' acceptance of games as a learning tool but a preference for traditional assessment methods.

Online discussions, despite offering bonus points for the best answer, yielded average participation. This suggests that

Fig. 2. Level of student participation in various activities

while incentives played a role in motivating students, they alone may not be sufficient to drive high levels of participation. It is evident that students are more likely to participate when they perceive an enjoyable and interactive element in the activities[17].

The results further indicate that additional incentives were effective only for the second quiz game. This finding underscores the need to carefully consider the design and implementation of incentives to ensure maximum impact on student engagement.

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this study, the impact of activity-based learning on third-year B.Tech Biotechnology students was explored, revealing its pivotal role in enhancing student engagement, academic performance, and course outcome achievement. A direct correlation was established between the number of activities and pass rates, underscoring the importance of active participation. Notably, students exhibited a preference for classroom activities, emphasizing the need for enjoyable, engaging activities. Incorporating interactive elements, such as quiz games, boosted participation, while online discussions, despite incentives, yielded moderate engagement. These findings highlight the significance of activity-based learning in higher education and the need to tailor activities to student preferences for optimal results.

However, the limitations of this study include a relatively small and specific sample size, potential bias in participant self-selection, a lack of exploration into broader contextual factors, and a reliance on subjective measures. The study's findings may not be easily generalized to other populations or contexts, and the short-term focus may not capture long-term effects.

In conclusion, activity-based learning holds significant potential in enhancing student engagement, academic performance, and the attainment of course outcomes. By considering student preferences, addressing barriers to participation, and incorporating enjoyable elements into activities, educators can create a conducive learning environment that maximizes student motivation and success. The insights gained from this study provide valuable guidance for educators and institutions in developing effective strategies and interventions to enhance student experiences and academic achievements. Further research is recommended to explore additional factors influencing student participation and the long-term impact of activity-based learning on students' educational journeys.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank the management of PSG College of Technology for providing research facilities. Furthermore, SS wishes to thank Prof. Sameer Sahasrabudhe, Prof. of Practice (Design), IIT Gandhinagar for his guidance and motivation, and all the members of the Active Learning Workshop group, mentored by Prof. Sahasrabudhe, for their support.

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